

Eastern England Secure Data Environment and VISTA Early Adopter Project: Final Report

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Final Report

1. Executive project summary

VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025. Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TRevolution standards and AI capabilities within the Eastern England Secure Data Environment¹ (EE-SDE). This final report presents an overview of the project aims, TRevolution capabilities adopted, activities and assessments undertaken, outputs produced and recommendations for improvements and continued use.

The aims of VISTA were to support and enhance existing SDE processes, demonstrating how large-scale AI-enabled research can be conducted safely, efficiently and consistently, whilst helping other TREs adopt these approaches. From the outset, VISTA was framed as a practical way to explore:

- How research involving artificial intelligence (AI) models can be safely supported within SDEs
- How semi-automation can be used to support the checking of research outputs before they leave the SDE
- How these complex technical processes can be governed, trusted and clearly explained to the public.

VISTA adopted three TRevolution capabilities: SATRE² aligns the EE-SDE with a community driven- specification adopted across UK TREs and now evolving to include federation and ML output control capabilities. SACRO³ enables more efficient and auditable disclosure checking by applying statistical disclosure control principles directly within analytical workflows. SACRO-ML⁴ extends this to machine learning models through ante-hoc and post-hoc risk assessments, including SafeModel evaluation and membership inference attack testing.

Patient and public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE)⁵ was embedded through existing EE-SDE structures, including the Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG). This ensured that development of SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML reflected public expectations around transparency, accountability and appropriate use of automation.

The VISTA project produced several outputs:

- A full SATRE self-assessment for the Eastern England SDE, confirming we met the standard in full and identifying a small number of areas recommended for further improvement
- Tested and refined SACRO tools for safer and more consistent checking of research outputs, now embedded into our routine service processes
- An AI Risk Assessment Toolkit⁶ developed and tested locally to support review of research using machine learning models
- Demonstrator examples showing how machine learning based researcher projects can be carried out safely within a secure environment
- Improved public-facing materials and clearer explanations for complex topics such as AI, governance and disclosure control
- Lessons-learned reports capturing practical experience from testing these approaches, shared to support others developing similar capabilities

In summary, VISTA tested and enhanced existing tools for safer health research, demonstrating their viability in a live TRE. The study focused on how research involving artificial intelligence (AI) models can be supported securely, consistently and at scale. This matters now because the use of AI in health research is growing quickly, and organisations need practical, tested ways to use it safely and responsibly. The VISTA project has shown how secure research environments can strengthen oversight while supporting innovative health research which benefits patients and the public.

2. Overview of TRevolution capabilities utilised

2.1.1. SATRE

SATRE⁷ is a community-driven framework for assessing and designing TREs so they align with best practice for secure handling of sensitive data in the UK; it underpins the TRevolution programme and defines common capabilities to enable comparison and interoperability between TREs. Preparations are underway to launch SATRE v2.0 which will extend the original specification to consider federation and tighter control of AI/ML outputs, areas needed to support cross-TRE working. SATRE v1.0, produced during DARE UK Phase 1, has already been adopted by TREs across academia, the NHS and industry, including the Eastern England SDE^{8,9} and is informing work related to the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The specification codifies principles, pillars and capabilities into a structured self-evaluation model providing a common language for operators, data controllers, accreditors, and researchers. VISTA is supporting the refinement of SATRE standard, contributing to the development of v2.0 of the standard alongside other DARE UK

adopters who are evaluating it within real TRE settings and providing recommendations to the product team.

2.1.2. SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking for Research Outputs

SACRO¹⁰ provides researchers and airlock managers with tools that improve the efficiency of disclosure risk assessment by highlighting potential risks to researchers and airlock managers by providing empirical risk information for tables and plots that would otherwise require labour intensive manual review. By separating risk measurement from release decisions, SACRO strengthens human oversight while improving the efficiency, auditability, and transparency of output checking. Its multilanguage components apply principles-based statistical disclosure control (SDC) during analysis, flagging potentially disclosive outputs, suggesting mitigations, and generating concise review artefacts designed to support rather than replace expert judgement. Through VISTA SACRO is being tested in real world settings alongside other DARE UK early adopters to evaluate its effectiveness for identifying disclosure risks as results are prepared for release.

2.1.3. SACRO-ML – Support for Machine Learning

SACRO-ML¹¹ is an open-source toolkit that helps TREs and researchers assess and manage disclosure risks from trained ML models prior to egress. It combines ante-hoc safeguards via a SafeModel component that evaluates privacy risk stemming from data, hyperparameters and architectures (and encourages best-practice such as differential-privacy optimisers), with post-hoc assessment through a unified suite of attack simulations. The framework first applies lightweight structural indicators to screen for potential disclosure risk, followed by more computationally expensive attacks such as membership-inference (e.g., Likelihood-Ratio Attack, LiRA) and attribute-inference. The package supports common workflows across Scikit-learn¹¹ and PyTorch¹², writes human-readable risk reports, and continues to add capabilities (e.g., enhanced PyTorch support and improved structural attacks in the v1.4 branch). Conceptually, SACRO-ML enables safe, reproducible science by providing TREs with a principled framework for assessing the export readiness of trained models, complementing existing TRE processes as machine learning becomes more widely used. VISTA is testing how SACRO-ML functions within the EE-SDE to support evidence-based disclosure control for models trained using sensitive health data.

3. Feedback on capabilities adopted

3.1. Utility of capabilities

3.1.1. SATRE

SATRE provides a structured TRE self-assessment framework, giving VISTA the foundation needed for a high-quality platform benchmarking process. Its consistent capabilities and statements helped the EE-SDE

organise evidence and communicate assurance across stakeholders (operators, data controllers, researchers), avoiding ad hoc descriptions of what “good” looks like. These statements supported a collaborative, panel-based approach that enabled consistent evidence interpretation, reduced individual bias, and strengthened the self--assessment (Table 1). The assessment outputs support clearer planning by turning broad TRE principles into a structured model identifying strengths and priority improvements. SATRE added practical value by offering more specificity for TREs, making capability gaps easier to identify. Working through SATRE highlighted opportunities that led to tangible changes, including better operational reporting, training needs analysis, and improved structuring of assurance evidence. The EE-SDE is supporting SATRE’s evolution to v2 through early adopter groups and collaboration cafés and played a major role in establishing a working group to adopt SATRE as a common reference framework¹⁴ and map it to key UK assurance standards such as the Digital Economy Act (DEA) 2017¹⁵ and ISO/IEC 27001:2022¹⁶. This alignment enabled reuse of evidence across different accreditations, reducing burden, strengthening trust, and supporting secure, collaborative, public benefit- use of data.

Domain	# of statements	Mandatory	Recommended	Optional	Overall
Computing Technology and Information Security	58	100%	93%	100%	97%
Data Management	34	100%	100%	100%	100%
Information Governance	37	100%	100%	100%	100%
Supporting Capabilities	18	100%	91%	N/A	94%
Overall Score	147	100%	95%	100%	98%

Table 1: The EE-SDE overall percentage scores for the four SATRE domains across the three different statement types.

3.1.2. SACRO

The SACRO toolset enables a more structured, standardised and semi-automated approach to SDC, complementing human oversight while providing clear and consistent reporting on potentially disclosive outputs. Its risk classification and triage features help airlock managers prioritise outputs that need deeper review, and its exception flagging capabilities identify specific cells or areas of concern, accelerating communication and clarification with researchers. Logging creates a transparent and accurate audit trail for all output checks, strengthening operational security and improving record keeping across research teams. By applying predefined risk thresholds uniformly, SACRO reduces variation in interpretation between output checkers and supports fairness and consistency in release decisions. The toolset also provides a

repeatable safety layer that supports proportional review, allowing teams to manage increasing submission volumes without equivalent increases in manual effort. EE-SDE airlock managers have observed that this combination of structured workflow, automated checks and clear exception reporting allows many low-risk outputs to be approved within one to two working days, compared with the typical three to five days required for fully manual review. Researcher feedback confirmed that ACRO can be integrated smoothly into researcher workflows, with semi-automated checks reliably supporting commonly used statistical outputs such as frequency tables, descriptive statistics and logistic/probit regression models, all of which are packaged into structured artefacts that improve the consistency and transparency of output review. Automated checks do not currently extend to graphical outputs (e.g., ggplot2 plots, boxplots, scatterplots) or to some methods such as Poisson regression, spline-based modelling and certain missing-data approaches. As a result, researchers noted that some analytical outputs still require full manual SDC before egress, meaning the tooling currently complements rather than replaces existing disclosure control practice. By surfacing risks earlier in the process, SACRO encourages improved researcher practice and reduces avoidable rework. Overall, it strengthens the work of output checkers and helps TREs standardise training and record keeping across research groups.

3.1.3. SACRO-ML

SACRO-ML and the nascent RELEASE-AI¹⁷ framework from the TRevolution team have enabled VISTA to create the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit, supporting the full TRE ML lifecycle from data access request (DAR) to feasibility, risk assessment, governance approval and model egress (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The EE-SDE ML project lifecycle

This toolkit has been established alongside a demonstrator use case. A trial project using synthetic data to train a model which can predict the likelihood of a person's diabetes status from their healthcare history. Through this use case, we were able to review our project feasibility and risk assessment approach while also trialling SACRO-ML across the full workflow from both researcher and airlock-manager perspectives. This helped ensure that installation and operational setup were feasible within the TRE workflow, and that core SafeModel functionality worked as intended, producing expected outputs to inform the researcher of

any disclosure risk associated with their model training process and provide additional evidence to support the Airlock manager's review before egress. Testing highlighted that using the SafeModel wrapper dramatically increased the training time for these models. Additional details are provided in Figure 3. This use case confirmed that the artefacts required to wrap the model for post-hoc attack simulations (such as Likelihood-Ratio Attack (LiRA), worst case, and structural attacks) can be successfully implemented to generate empirical disclosure risk assessments, and that standardised reports and JSON outputs can support consistent output-checking processes. Feedback on our second demonstrator use case for the SACRO-ML trial is expected but has not yet been received, this reflects the longer onboarding period associated with the project's evolving research objectives rather than any lack of progress. As the scope and focus of the work continued to develop and mature, the contracting and data-access processes required additional review to ensure alignment. The introduction of a new data pipeline revealed some early issues that required correction and resulted in a short delay to the final data delivery. This was subsequently compounded by temporary constraints on researcher availability, which also contributed to the extended timeline. As a result, the use-case insights will emerge after the formal end of the VISTA project; however, we remain fully committed to providing this feedback to the SACRO-ML team and ensuring the trial continues to be informative and valuable for the TRevolution community.

3.2. Impact of capabilities

3.2.1. SATRE

The SATRE assessment (Table 1) strengthened the EE-SDE's operational maturity by providing a structured, evidence-based lens through which to evaluate both established and emerging capabilities. By highlighting partially developed controls, particularly around documentation packaging, user-facing clarity and governance transparency, the assessment enabled the EE-SDE to make targeted improvements that enhanced assurance without disrupting existing workflows. This included the introduction of AWS-based security and configuration dashboards (such as GuardDuty & Security Hub CSPM), which consolidate platform-wide findings into a single operational view. These dashboards offer consistent, real-time visibility of vulnerabilities, misconfigurations and remediation progress, improving oversight and supporting more predictable governance.

The assessment contributed to the refinement of internal data management processes. Data harmonisation and tagged ETL (Extract Transform Load) pipelines have made data transformations traceable from ingestion through to researcher use, embedding transparency directly into the data processing lifecycle. Research teams and auditors now receive structured artefacts documenting how datasets are produced, improving reproducibility and trust. In parallel, a targeted training needs analysis led to role-specific training

pathways, including mandatory SDC modules, aligning staff capability with emerging operational requirements.

Several capabilities already in place were validated through the assessment, including automated configuration validation and long-term archiving in standard formats. These controls underpin operational resilience by reducing manual workload and supporting sustainable data stewardship. The SATRE process also clarified priority areas for further development, such as streamlining metadata cataloguing, improving user-facing documentation and aligning onboarding with emerging NHS SDE expectations. These activities ensure that workflows remain clear, data assets more discoverable and the platform interoperable with national standards.

Collectively, the improvements informed by SATRE have strengthened EE-SDE's governance, increased transparency for partners and enhanced readiness for future assurance frameworks. The assessment has shaped a forward roadmap grounded in evidence, positioning the EE-SDE to support scalable, privacy protecting research aligned with the evolving national health data ecosystem.

3.2.2. SACRO

Adopting SACRO at the EE-SDE strengthened the operational delivery of SDC by embedding semi-automated checking into researcher workflows and airlock manager review processes. SACRO was implemented and tested end-to-end, from researcher analysis using ACRO in R and Python, through structured output packaging with ACRO, to formal review in SACRO Viewer and final release decisions. This practical integration shifted SDC from bespoke and manually intensive processes to structured, repeatable checks, improving consistency, transparency, and organisational readiness for increasingly complex analytical outputs. Through this work, operational processes and governance were strengthened by incorporating SDC into routine analytical workflows.

Researchers now initiate ACRO sessions, generate outputs under defined risk profiles, and package their results in a standardised format containing embedded metadata and configuration settings. As a result, outputs arrive for review already assessed against agreed thresholds and rules, reducing ambiguity and variability in what is submitted. Security and consistency were further enhanced through systematic application of organisational risk thresholds and disclosure control profiles. SACRO allows the configuration of defined risk parameters, such as safe thresholds, small cell rules, zero value handling and checks for missing data, ensuring that assessments reflect consistent criteria rather than subjective judgement. Testing included exploration of differing threshold configurations and borderline cases to understand how risk flags behave in practice. This structured approach reduces the likelihood of unsafe release due to oversight and

ensures that similar outputs are treated consistently across projects, strengthening security, fairness and trust in decision-making.

On the reviewer side, SACRO Viewer supports a more consistent and accountable process by enabling structured inspection of outputs exposing the risk settings applied, and recording formal approve/reject decisions. This has clarified responsibilities between researchers and output checkers, reduced reliance on informal interpretation of policy, and improved the defensibility of release decisions

Notably for SDEs, the introduction of SACRO improves the efficiency of output review without diminishing human oversight or accountability. By automatically surfacing potential disclosure risks both at the point of output creation and during review, SACRO supports quicker triage of low-risk outputs and clearer identification of items requiring deeper scrutiny. This enables reviewers to focus effort proportionately according to risk, rather than treating all outputs uniformly. Crucially, SACRO does not automate approval decisions; rather, it supports expert judgement by providing structured evidence and highlighting areas of concern. This balance between automation and human control improves workflow efficiency while upholding strong governance.

Additionally, organisational capacity, preparedness, and transparency were strengthened as SACRO was exercised across multiple output types in realistic operational scenarios. This process enhanced internal expertise in applying semi-automated SDC and made risk configurations more explicit through the structured artefacts generated during review. Decisions are now recorded and communicated with greater clarity, supporting strong, audit readiness and improving stakeholder engagement. Collectively, these developments further reinforce the EE-SDE's capability to manage complex or high-volume output demands and position the organisation well for future assurance expectations.

Finally, the implementation delivered wider organisational and sector benefits by demonstrating how semi-automated SDC tooling can be integrated into real TRE workflows. It showed that structured disclosure control processes can be embedded within common analysis environments such as R and Python while remaining aligned with formal review and release governance. This contributes to broader efforts across the TRE community to standardise and strengthen SDC practice, helping to ensure that outputs are subject to consistent, documented, and transparent checks prior to release.

3.2.3. SACRO-ML

Adding SACRO-ML to our disclosure control toolkit has expanded the EE-SDE's ability to support machine learning research by enabling structured disclosure control for models trained on sensitive healthcare data. This capability allows the EE-SDE to accept a wider range of ML projects while maintaining confidence that

disclosure risks can be evaluated consistently and transparently. Although SACRO-ML is still developing and currently supports a defined set of model families, its integration marks a significant step in strengthening TRE governance of AI research and preparing for future assurance expectations.

This proof of concept demonstrated how SACRO-ML can be embedded directly into both researcher workflows and output checking processes, showing that disclosure risk assessment can function as an integral part of model development rather than as a late-stage addition. Researchers can prepare supported model types using SafeModel wrappers and produce structured artefacts that record model configuration, training parameters and potential risk indicators in a standardised check file. This ante-hoc assessment reduces avoidable issues early in development and encourages more defensible modelling decisions. In parallel, output checkers apply SACRO-ML's simulated attack framework to generate consistent evidence on membership inference and related risks before any model is considered for release. Together these steps improve predictability, reproducibility and accountability across the EE-SDE's ML workflow (Figure 2).

The TRevolution team delivered the first version of the RELEASE AI framework in 2025, which informed the development of the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit. This enabled the team to implement an example of the RELEASE AI governance and evaluation phases where the EE-SDE holds responsibility for oversight. The toolkit incorporates SACRO-ML's disclosure control process together with structured questions capturing researchers' ML plans and provides guidance for feasibility review that identifies risks and proposes appropriate Five Safes¹⁸ based controls for any egressed models. These controls may include secure hosting, role-based access controls, restrictions on model queries and limits on further model training. This approach allows a TRE to manage risk through proportionate governance rather than requiring trained models to demonstrate no disclosure risk in isolation. It supports the delivery of public benefit while ensuring individual privacy remains protected.

Together, SACRO-ML and the RELEASE AI framework have strengthened EE-SDE's readiness for a rapidly evolving AI governance landscape. By combining early-stage risk capture with empirical model egress testing, the EE-SDE is well positioned to support ML projects that can benefit patient care and decision making while maintaining strong privacy protections.

3.3. Public involvement and engagement

VISTA did not produce a standalone PPIE strategy; instead, public engagement was embedded within the established EE-SDE PPIE framework to ensure alignment with recognised governance and good practice. This approach allowed the project to build on mature structures, avoid duplication and maintain meaningful

public involvement. Engagement was delivered primarily through the Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG)¹⁹, a diverse group from the East of England and East Midlands that meets regularly to provide public challenge, insight and governance advice.

VISTA was introduced to CPAG in April 2025²⁰, and contributors were briefed on the project's aims, timelines and expected outputs. From the start, the work focused on three core questions: 1) how AI and automation can support TREs safely, 2) how research outputs should be reviewed before leaving an environment, and 3) how technical processes can be governed and clearly explained to the public.

Two core technical workstreams underpin the project. SATRE supports standardisation of how TREs are built and operated. SACRO and SACRO-ML strengthen SDC and enable semi-automated output checking. Although technical, these strands led contributors to focus on broader issues including trust, transparency, accountability and proportional oversight. Contributors consistently stressed that technology should strengthen governance and not replace human judgement.

Public contributors wanted assurance that their input would shape national practice. With the EE-SDE mapped to SATRE standards, contributors could see a clear route for their input to inform national TRE development. Several CPAG members also took part in the first TREvolution Collaboration Café; some found the format unfamiliar but valued the openness, shared learning and transparency. All feedback was submitted to the TREvolution team to support further refinement of their approach.

Embedding VISTA within the established EE-SDE structures enabled sustained dialogue on AI governance, disclosure risk, explainability and appropriate use of automation. Contributors responded positively when the team explained that SACRO highlights areas of higher disclosure risk for human reviewers, and SACRO-ML provides model specific disclosure control for machine learning projects, and human oversight remains essential.

Concerns were raised about the absence of a standardised AI governance policy across DARE UK partners and explanations were provided highlighting that organisations rely on local arrangements, and that work is underway on shared principles. A direction of travel was agreed with CPAG, focused on shared risk frameworks.

Contributors also asked about the risks of machine learning models memorising sensitive data. In response, the team committed to developing a structured AI risk framework, layered review processes and architectural improvements to strengthen explainability and safety.

Reassurance was also sought on testing and deployment. A shared agreement was reached to adopt a staged and cautious approach, prioritising controlled testing and risk mitigation. Questions about federation were noted; and assurances given that early work focuses on demonstrating the approach within the EE-SDE before exploring wider application.

Human oversight was emphasised throughout the discussions, with reassurances given that researchers are unable to download data, that comprehensive monitoring controls are in place, and that the EE-SDE maintains ISO 27001 certification and undergoes routine penetration testing. Airlock managers retain final control over output release, with SACRO acting as a supporting tool rather than a replacement for human review.

Contributors observed that acronyms and technical language posed barriers to engagement, prompting requests for clearer explanations and improved visibility of how their feedback influenced decision-making. In response, the team developed plain English materials, glossaries, accessible summaries and regular feedback loops.

CPAG reviewed the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit in March 2026. Providing clear explanations of model training, testing, risk assessment and egress enabled contributors to interrogate complex governance matters effectively. Their feedback guided both refinements to the toolkit and plans for its further development.

Overall, VISTA demonstrated that public contributors can meaningfully influence complex AI governance work when supported with clear information and structured opportunities for dialogue. Their involvement strengthened accountability and transparency, helping to ensure that AI and automation augments rather than replaces human judgement.

3.4. Overall drawbacks and recommendations for improvement

3.4.1. SATRE

The SATRE assessment highlighted challenges in applying the standard in practice and identified ways SATRE could better support TREs completing assessments.

The SATRE standard in some areas was designed around on-prem assumptions for TREs, and the instructions do not fully account for modern cloud-native development realities. Clause 2.2.5 (“development environment mirrors production”) does not fully reflect common cloud IAM (Identity and Access Management) constraints, multi-stage pipelines or security boundaries; a four-stage model

(development, test, stage and production) was necessary. The current wording may lead to ambiguity and potentially non-compliant interpretations. This could be improved by rewriting the clause to explicitly support modern cloud patterns, multi-stage environments, automated deployments, and IAM-based differences that still meet equivalence, shifting to a more principle-based approach.

The cost-related clauses do not reflect variable, usage-based cloud charging. Clauses 2.3.1, 4.4.1, 4.4.2 expect transparent and predictable project costs, but do not consider cloud consumption models where compute and storage are pay-as-you-go. This makes it difficult for TREs to evidence compliance in a way that aligns with SATRE's expectations. Our recommendation is to update costing requirements to explicitly accommodate usage-metered, elastic cloud models, including guidance on fixed onboarding costs, variable usage, cost alerts, and user-controlled scaling.

3.4.2. SACRO

SACRO does not support all statistical methods, either because they have not yet been implemented or because some are considered low risk from an SDC perspective. This uneven coverage creates different workflow routes for researchers and airlock managers, depending on whether an output is supported, partially supported, or unsupported. The Airlock Manager Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) reflects this through its forked pathway, highlighting the complexity of integrating SACRO into existing disclosure processes.

The main challenge is the breadth of analytical methods SACRO supports. Researchers often use mixed workflows that include both SACRO supported and unsupported techniques, meaning they must move between semi-automated and manual processes. Airlock managers must likewise identify the correct pathway for each output type, adding operational burden and reducing process consistency.

SACRO currently supports many commonly used statistical models, including linear, logistic, and probit regression, which benefit from automated checks. However, several routine analytical diagnostics, such as correlation matrices, variance inflation factor (VIF) tables, and some robustness or sensitivity checks, are not yet supported.

These outputs therefore require manual review. For example, when a researcher produces a correlation matrix or VIF table to assess multicollinearity, output checkers must manually confirm that no small or sensitive counts are indirectly disclosed, increasing workload and review variability. Our recommendation is for the SACRO developers to consider how the SACRO outputs currently used by the SACRO viewer could be integrated into a TRE's broader egress management tool chain, reducing the need for different

processes between SACRO supported and other outputs and providing a more seamless experience for both researchers and airlock managers.

3.4.3. SACRO-ML

A key challenge is the extended and sometimes inconsistent runtimes observed during full SACRO-ML assessments. End-to-end execution typically ranges from approximately 90 to 120 minutes, with the SafeModel k-anonymity stage and shadow model attack generation accounting for most of this duration. Runtime measurements were recorded using both wall-clock time and CPU time, which showed near-identical values, indicating minimal impact from I/O or disk bottlenecks.

Figure 3: Comparison of Baseline Model and SafeModel Wrapper across increasing dataset sizes, showing substantial increase in CPU and wall time for SafeModel while memory usage grows moderately for both. Time taken to train a model, SACRO-ML SafeModel vs standard process in seconds for different input record sizes, 5,000 to 20,000.

Performance profiling demonstrates that runtimes increase with dataset size, reaching approximately 25–30 minutes at 15,000 records and 40–45 minutes at 20,000 records. A further validation at 25,000 records resulted in a runtime of approximately 54 minutes, supporting the observed scaling trend. All experiments were conducted on a consistent compute environment (AWS m6a.xlarge instance) to ensure comparability, as different instance types can significantly affect CPU and memory performance.

A configurable SafeModel Light mode for exploratory work would allow faster iteration while retaining mandatory use of the full configuration for any pre-egress checks. Given the long runtime of SafeModel wrapper and attack stages, additional features such as progress indicators, resource monitoring and optional checkpointing could improve usability by allowing researchers to track long-running processes and resume workflows if computational failures occur.

A second challenge relates to error handling and pre-flight validation. Users still encounter preventable issues including array shape mismatches, missing or incorrectly named artefacts and directory permission errors. These problems lead to repeated trial and error and unnecessary compute spend. Automated pre-run validation that checks array compatibility, artefact presence, model suitability and writable output paths would resolve most failures before execution begins. Clear, human readable error messages and a one click sanity check in the template notebooks would further reduce support needs.

Finally, testing confirmed the importance of reducing first time setup friction. Although documentation and example workflows have improved, users benefit from ready to run notebooks and explicit environment checks. Providing four standardised notebooks covering Target wrapping, Worst Case, LiRA and SafeModel workflows, each with validation cells, resource guidance and storage path checks, would speed adoption. A short onboarding guide explaining artefact discipline, consistent feature ordering and minimum submission requirements would help new users complete a successful first run more quickly.

While the recently released documentation website for SACRO-ML has improved some of these matters, our recommendation is that continued improvement and additional refinements to the tooling, would reduce friction, improve consistency and enhance the operational reliability of SACRO-ML, ultimately enabling TREs to support ML projects more efficiently and with greater confidence in their disclosure risk assessments.

4. Feedback on adoption process

4.1. Challenges encountered and how these were identified

During adoption of SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML, a number of practical and organisational challenges were identified, including terminology alignment across assurance frameworks, availability of suitable demonstrator use cases, early versioning constraints within the ACRO Python library, and interpretation of optional SATRE clauses. These issues were surfaced through routine assurance reviews, early operational testing and engagement with adopters, and informed both the project's lessons learned and subsequent recommendations.

Looking ahead, the inclusion of a TRE maturity model within SATRE version 2, aligned to the significance of each clause, would help new TREs determine which optional features are essential from the outset and which can be deferred or excluded depending on their operational needs.

4.2. Recommendations for improving the adoption process

4.2.1. SATRE

To strengthen future adoption and support consistent implementation across organisations, it would be strategically beneficial to develop an induction pack to accompany SATRE standard and scoring logic. This would provide clearer orientation for new adopters, streamline onboarding, and help ensure more effective and confident use of the framework from the outset. A key component could be a library of evidence templates, supported by exemplar entries that illustrate high-quality responses across different requirements. This would streamline evidence development and provide teams with clearer expectations for articulating compliance. Complementing this, exemplar training plans tailored to different SATRE-relevant roles would help organisations develop appropriate internal capability, ensuring that staff involved in governance, technical processes, or oversight receive training aligned with their responsibilities. The existing mappings between SATRE and other relevant TRE standards such as ISO/IEC 27001:2022, NHS DSPT²¹ or DEA 2017 offer a useful foundation for this work. These mappings can assist TREs that already meet other accreditation frameworks to more rapidly understand their SATRE position, while also enabling organisations to use SATRE as a structured pathway towards these other standards. Providing guidance on common implementation and validation challenges would further support new adopters, helping to reduce recurring issues and promote smoother, more consistent adoption. Beyond written materials, the onboarding journey could be enhanced through ongoing peer support mechanisms, such as online

discussion forums, mailing groups or periodic community meetings, facilitating shared learning and collaborative problem solving. Finally, developing an improved plain language summary of the standard and its benefits would enhance PPIE activity by making SATRE's purpose, value, and implications more accessible to public contributors, service users, and non-technical stakeholders.

4.2.2. SACRO

Over the course of the VISTA project, the SACRO team made significant enhancements to their documentation and training materials, notably through the resources available on <https://sacro-tools.org/> and <https://outputchecking.org/>. Further developing these materials and ensuring stronger alignment between them would support TRevolution adopters in locating and navigating the full suite of guidance more efficiently. A more unified view of the available resources would help both researchers and airlock managers understand the principles-based approach that underpins SACRO, identify relevant training opportunities, and access peer support networks such as SDC REBOOT. This would contribute to greater consistency and assurance across the TRE ecosystem. As adoption of SACRO expands, maintaining clear routes for user to engage with ongoing peer learning opportunities will be increasingly important. Both new and experienced practitioners benefit from sharing operational challenges, emerging solutions and examples of effective practice. Continued investment in clear, accessible documentation, increased clarity around training pathways and strengthened peer support mechanisms will collectively enable broader, more confident and more consistent adoption of the SACRO toolset across the TRE community.

4.2.3. SACRO-ML

As work progresses on supporting machine learning in TREs, there is a clear opportunity to strengthen the adoption journey for both SACRO-ML and the wider RELEASE AI process. A natural next step is to develop ML-specific equivalents to the existing output checker and researcher disclosure-control training, so that users can understand how disclosure risk manifests in model development as well as in traditional statistical outputs. Online courses, or an addendum to the Safe Data Access Professional SDC handbook²² tailored to ML disclosure control, would provide a consistent foundation for researchers, TRE staff and airlock managers who are encountering these issues for the first time. In parallel, continued development of the RELEASE AI process, supported by template approaches and case studies that illustrate different aspects of the process, would help organisations translate the concepts into day-to-day practice. Case studies that show how TREs define and apply risk appetite when assessing ML workflows would be particularly useful, because these decisions often vary across environments and users benefit from understanding the

spectrum of possible approaches. Integrating the RELEASE AI process into a website such as <https://outputchecking.org/>, for example alongside the resources already available at sacro-tools.org, would support the creation of a single, coherent environment where adopters can access consolidated guidance, illustrative examples and supporting materials. Integrating these components would provide TREs and researchers with a clearer, end-to-end pathway through the additional considerations introduced by machine learning workflows, from model development to output release, and would promote a more consistent and assured application of disclosure control principles across the TRE community.

4.3. Lessons learned

The VISTA project highlighted the value of close collaboration between adopters and product teams. Responsive engagement from the SACRO team and participation in the SATRE Short Life Working Group (SLWG) enabled shared understanding, rapid issue resolution and the co-development of reusable outputs. Joint PPIE activity with PANORAMA also demonstrated the benefit of coordinated engagement when explaining complex disclosure control concepts to public contributors.

The project also identified opportunities to improve coordination. Training materials for SACRO and SACRO-ML were developed independently by multiple partners resulting in avoidable duplication. Documentation was distributed across different platforms, requiring adopters to piece together guidance from multiple sources. Earlier visibility of the RELEASE AI framework would have supported better alignment and reduced rework. Addressing these issues would streamline adoption, reduce friction and improve consistency for future users.

The project also encountered operational challenges that contributed to extended timelines. The data-access request process for the demonstrator use cases took longer than anticipated, and project plans evolved during delivery. For the machine-learning use case, the focus evolved from model training to validation as the work progressed. While the team adjusted accordingly, this shift meant that the project was presented to the Data Access Committee (DAC) in a form that differed from the original DAR submission, which in turn extended the approvals process. Earlier and more structured consultation with the researcher could have helped maintain alignment and reduced uncertainty for the DAC. Due to the extended approvals process, we developed a synthetic testing approach for SACRO-ML later in the process, having this in place from the outset would have accelerated the feedback cycle to the SACRO team. Looking ahead, providing exemplar datasets or test cases alongside TRevolution products would help

future adopters test technical feasibility early, while navigating governance requirements for real-world use cases.

Engagement activities hosted by the TRevolution programme yielded variable levels of participation and impact. The Collaboration Cafés offered a welcoming forum for community building and public perspectives, but it was not always clear how discussions influenced product development. This contrasted with more structured groups, such as the SATRE SLWG, which had clearer objectives and more visible outcomes.

Another challenge arose from the dispersed nature of TRevolution documentation. Key materials were distributed across multiple websites and Git repositories, requiring adopters to search <https://github.com/AI-SDC> and more recently <https://sacro-tools.org/> and <https://outputchecking.org/> to piece together the full picture for SACRO disclosure control tools and documentation. Establishing a single front door for TRevolution products, with consistent signposting, integrated documentation and licensing for reuse would greatly improve the adopter journey.

Together, these lessons highlight both the strengths of the collaborative environment developed during VISTA and the improvements that would most enhance the experience of future adopters. Strengthening coordination across product teams, ensuring early clarity on processes and documentation, and providing more structured communication channels will support smoother adoption and help build on the strong foundations established through this project.

5. Conclusions and future direction

5.1. Conclusions

The VISTA project has demonstrated the significant value that structured assurance frameworks and emerging disclosure control tooling can bring to a modern TRE such as the EE-SDE. By adopting and implementing SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML within live TRE operations, the project has strengthened the EE-SDE's technical maturity, governance processes and readiness to support increasingly complex analytical and machine learning research.

The work has also contributed meaningful insights to the wider TRevolution programme, helping shape the direction of standards and tools that will underpin future cross-TRE collaboration. A key achievement has been how SATRE provided a consistent, evidence-based approach for assessing and enhancing the EE-

SDE. The self-assessment process encouraged deeper reflection across technical, operational and governance teams, highlighted localised areas for improvement, and reinforced the importance of transparent, well-structured assurance for both users and decision-makers.

SACRO and SACRO-ML further advanced operational capability by introducing more standardised, auditable and scalable approaches to disclosure control for both traditional statistical outputs and trained machine learning models. Together, these tools have helped embed a culture of proportional, defensible risk management across the research lifecycle.

Equally important were the lessons gained about communication, coordination and usability. The project highlighted the need for clearer, earlier alignment between product teams and adopters, and for more streamlined documentation pathways. The experience emphasised the value of developing a single front door to TRevolution products so adopters can more easily navigate guidance, training and technical materials. Engagement with public contributors reinforced the central role of transparency, explainability and human oversight in maintaining public trust as automation and AI-enabled tooling evolve.

Overall, VISTA has been a highly constructive learning exercise that has strengthened the EE-SDE, contributed directly to national TRE standards and built a foundation for future AI-ready, privacy preserving research. The insights gained will continue to shape our development roadmap and support the wider TRE ecosystem as it moves toward more integrated, standardised and trusted approaches to secure data access.

5.2. Future use of TRevolution capability

Over the course of VISTA, the EE-SDE team has integrated SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML into standard policies and procedures, and as SATRE v2 becomes available we will incorporate relevant insights. While SATRE provides valuable guidance for the TRE community, we must balance its recommendations with our broader obligations, including ISO/IEC 27001:2022, DSPT, emerging SDE accreditation under the DEA 2017, and expectations under the Health Data Research Service (HDRS), to ensure that our roadmap, security controls and governance policies remain coherent and proportionate.

A core dimension of future expansion will be our engagement with RELEASE AI and the wider TRE community to broaden the range of machine learning model architectures that can be trained securely within the EE-SDE. We will work to ensure that such models can be deployed to deliver public benefit under appropriate controls that prevent unintended use or manipulation that could reveal personal information about contributors.

The EE-SDE is part of the recently funded Dare UK Real-world Research Exemplar Programme project, CONNECT AF Stroke, which evaluates cross region cardiovascular outcomes through federated analytics across SAIL Databank, the EE-SDE, and Dementias Platform UK. Through this work we support harmonised governance, contribute operational insight into SATRE-aligned architecture, and enable federated execution within the EE-SDE. These activities provide a practical environment for testing and refining privacy preserving methods and strengthening readiness for future federated research.

We will continue engaging with the broader TRevolution product ecosystem and identify reusable implementations that can strengthen the EE-SDE capabilities. Consistent with our Business-As-Usual (BAU) approach, we will maintain operational use, structured testing and systematic user feedback, sharing learning with DARE UK and the wider TRE community and contributing to cross-TRE evaluation where priorities allow.

5.3. Support needed for continued or expanded use

Ongoing operational use, structured testing and systematic user feedback will ensure continued support for the DARE UK VISTA outputs, including SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML, within the EE-SDE. Engagement with peer networks such as SDC REBOOT and PEDRI ill remain important for sharing learning, aligning approaches and refining standards and tools as TREs adopt more advanced capabilities like model disclosure control.

Training and capacity building will continue across technical, governance and operational teams through applied use of VISTA outputs. Further training on ACRO enabled workflows, risk thresholds, secondary disclosure risks, Safe Model concepts, attack simulations and model egress review will help ensure consistent adoption. There is also a growing need for plain language PPIE resources to explain how SACRO and SACRO-ML enhance safety, support human oversight, and enable trustworthy research.

Sustained use of VISTA outputs will be delivered through existing operational teams and funding routes, where this aligns with BAU priorities. Additional DARE UK support would enable us to go further and faster: accelerating comparative evaluation, expanded user testing and deeper workflow integration. We will continue sharing lessons learned and user feedback to support wider uptake across the TRE ecosystem and welcome coordinated work on shared documentation and case studies.

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Additional VISTA Reports:

- Eastern England SDE: SATRE Self Assessment: Findings, Insights and Iterations
- Eastern England SDE: Scaling Safe Outputs with SACRO Integration
- Eastern England SDE: Safe Models, Safe AI – Governance and Disclosure Testing
- Eastern England SDE: Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) Learnings
- VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit
- Eastern England SDE Statistical Disclosure Control Training Presentation
- Eastern England SDE Airlock Manager Statistical Disclosure Control SOP
- Eastern England SDE Researcher Statistical Disclosure Control SOP
- Eastern England Airlock Manager Model Disclosure Control SOP

- Eastern England SDE Researcher Model Disclosure Control SOP

6. Glossary

Five Safes – A widely used framework for designing and assessing safe access to sensitive data across five dimensions: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data and Safe Outputs (considered together to achieve “safe use”)

Airlock Manager - A data security role in Trusted Research Environments, responsible for reviewing and approving data transfers.

CPAG – Core Public Advisory Group, the patient and public advisory group established for the Eastern England Secure Data Environment.

DARE UK – Data and Analytics Research Environments UK, is a programme aimed towards establishing a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments.

DAC – Data Access Committee, the group of governance, subject matter experts and members of the public who review and make access decisions for a given TRE.

DAR – Data Access Request, the form or document completed by a researcher to describe their research question and data needs so an access decision can be made for a given TRE.

DEA accreditation (2017) - Digital Economy Act (2017) accreditation, demonstrates that an institution meets a set of criteria that individuals, organisations and research projects laid out in the Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria

EE-SDE – Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

ISO/IEC 27001:2022 – The international standard that sets requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an Information Security Management System (ISMS) to manage information security risks.

ML – Machine Learning, statistical algorithms that can learn from data

NHS DSPT – NHS Data Protection and Security Toolkit is an online self-assessment tool for health and care organisations to measure performance against the National Data Guardian’s 10 data security standards and GDPR requirements

PEDRI – Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative, is a UK-wide partnership including NHS England, aimed at improving public involvement in health data research.

PPIE – Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement is the active partnership between researchers and the public to shape health research.

K-anonymity - is a data privacy model. It helps reduce the risk of re-identification attacks by grouping or masking data until the unique combinations of quasi-identifiers appear at least 'k' times in the data. In other words, the probability of identifying an individual based on combinations of attributes is no more than

1/k.SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and Machine Learning, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained Machine Learning models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SafeModel – A wrapper around a machine learning model in SACRO-ML that enforces disclosure risk checks and records information needed to assess whether the model is safe to release.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

TREvolution – A DARE UK programme developing and testing standards and reference implementations to support more consistent, interoperable Trusted Research Environments (TREs), including components such as SATRE (architecture/specification) and related tooling

VISTA – Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI, is the project package aimed towards delivering tools to enhance Statistical Disclosure Checking, support in TREs for Machine Learning, and also for establishing a benchmarking standard for Trusted Research Environments.

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